

CHATBOTS IN ESL TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Abstract. *Modern teaching methods for English as a second language (ESL) increasingly integrate digital technologies, among which chatbots occupy a special place. These software systems can simulate human dialogue, provide instant feedback, and adapt to the user's level of knowledge. These capabilities make chatbots an effective tool for developing all language skills: reading, writing, speaking, and listening. Their use creates unique conditions for individualized learning and student motivation, which is especially important given the limited time available for in-person classes and the diverse needs of students.*

Keywords: *Chatbots; Foreign language competence; Independent learning; Interactive learning; Artificial intelligence, Writing skill*

Introduction. It's impossible to imagine the modern world without technology, which permeates all spheres of life, including education. Artificial intelligence is gradually becoming an integral part of the educational process, and its use in foreign language teaching is becoming increasingly popular. Among the many tools of digital pedagogy, chatbots—software systems capable of natural language dialogue and interaction with the user—occupy a special place. In the context of teaching English as a foreign language (ESL), chatbots allow for the creation of an interactive environment where students can develop language skills without constant teacher supervision.

The relevance of using chatbots in ESL teaching is driven by several factors. Firstly, modern educational practices face limited time for individual lessons and a lack of resources to fully educate each student. Secondly, student motivation often depends on interactivity and the ability to receive instant feedback. Chatbots help create such an environment: they facilitate constant interaction, adapt to each student's level of knowledge, and provide correct assignment solutions and explanations for errors. As a result, the learning process becomes more engaging and effective. The purpose of this article is to explore the potential of using chatbots in ESL teaching methods.

The focus of this article is on teaching English as a foreign language using digital technologies. The analysis focuses on the use of chatbots to develop students' language skills, including writing, speaking, reading, and listening.

The study's methods include an analysis of modern pedagogical sources, observation of student interactions with chatbots, and an analysis of the results of practical exercises and tests completed with their help. This comprehensive approach allows us to identify key features of chatbot use and evaluate their effectiveness in real-world learning situations.

The scientific novelty of this study lies in analyzing the pedagogical potential of AI-based chatbots in teaching English as a second language within the context of Kazakhstani education. Unlike previous studies, this research focuses on adapting chatbot technologies to local educational conditions, emphasizing independent learning, learner motivation, and the development of core language skills. Furthermore, attention is paid to adaptability and individualization of learning, reflecting current trends in digital pedagogy. The practical significance of this work lies in the potential use of the presented materials and recommendations for lesson planning, creating interactive

exercises, and integrating digital technologies into everyday learning. The findings may be useful for teachers, methodologists, and educational platform developers.

In the context of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the issue of integrating artificial intelligence technologies into foreign language education is becoming increasingly relevant. The national education system is undergoing active digital transformation, which requires the introduction of innovative teaching tools aimed at improving the quality of language education. Despite the growing interest in artificial intelligence in pedagogy, the methodological potential of chatbots in teaching English as a second language within Kazakhstani educational institutions remains insufficiently studied. This creates a need for research focused on adapting global digital practices to local educational conditions.

The Benefits and Potential of AI-Based Chatbots for Language Learning. The use of AI-based chatbots in ESL teaching has been actively studied in both international and national research contexts. While foreign studies mainly focus on technological advancement and large-scale digital platforms, Kazakhstani researchers emphasize pedagogical adaptation, learner motivation, and the role of chatbots in supporting independent learning. According to Esirkep et al. (2025), chatbots contribute to the development of intelligent educational systems by providing personalized support and adaptive feedback, which is particularly relevant for the educational environment of Kazakhstan. Additionally, educational and game-based chatbots are distinguished: the former aim to systematize knowledge, while the latter enhance motivation through gamification. Each of these approaches is actively used in educational practice, enabling an adaptive approach to learning and continuous monitoring of material acquisition. [1]

In recent years, the scientific field has actively studied the impact of chatbots on the teaching of English as a second language. It has been shown that students who regularly interact with chatbots demonstrate higher levels of written literacy and active speaking. One of the most relevant areas is the use of chatbots for independent practice, allowing students to practice language skills without the constant presence of a teacher. In this context, it is noted that chatbots can adapt tasks to the student's level of knowledge, providing individualized learning and enabling the development of both basic and advanced language competencies.

Modern educational platforms offer chatbot integration with various ESL tools. For example, bots can assess spelling and grammar, offer corrections and explanations, and create tasks focused on developing specific skills. Recent research shows that a combined approach, including in-person classes and chatbots, increases student motivation and promotes deeper learning. Particular attention is paid to the development of interactive scenarios where students engage in dialogue with the bot in real or simulated situations, creating conditions for speaking practice and improving listening skills.

At the theoretical level, several key advantages of using chatbots are highlighted. Firstly, accessibility: interaction with the bot is possible anytime and anywhere. Secondly, instant feedback allows students to correct errors immediately after they occur, which contributes to the development of lasting language skills. Thirdly, the use of chatbots promotes independence, responsibility for their own learning, and an active approach to language learning. In the Kazakhstani educational context, similar conclusions were reached by Hamza and Zagidullina (2025), who investigated the integration of chatbots into foreign language education. Their study highlights that chatbots increase student engagement and motivation, particularly in conditions where classroom time is limited. The authors emphasize that chatbots serve not only as a technological tool but also as a pedagogical assistant that supports learners in autonomous language practice. [2]

Recent research highlights that chatbots are particularly effective for students learning English as a second language, as they create a safe environment for practice without the fear of making mistakes in front of the teacher or classmates. Bots allow for the simulation of real-life dialogues and situational tasks, which develops practical skills needed in real-life communication. Furthermore, modern systems can adapt to students' interests, offering content related to their professional field, hobbies, or current topics, which increases engagement and promotes active language practice.

Recent publications highlight new approaches to integrating chatbots into ESL. For example, blended learning methods, where chatbots are used as a supplement to traditional lessons, are actively discussed. This approach provides a balance between live interaction with the teacher and independent practice with the bot. Particular attention is paid to developing writing skills through automated tasks and dialogue exercises, which improves sentence construction accuracy and enriches vocabulary. Similarly, research by Esirkep et al. demonstrated the potential role of chatbots in enhancing intelligent educational systems, emphasizing personalized support and adaptability in learning environments. [3]

New research shows that chatbots not only help practice language skills but also contribute to the development of cognitive competencies: logical thinking, information analysis, and the ability to formulate thoughts coherently and clearly. The use of bots in ESL teaching is seen as a promising approach, providing students with access to an interactive, flexible, and motivating learning environment. This makes it possible to more effectively develop language competence in a modern education environment. [4]

Implementing AI-powered chatbot systems for English language learning (ESL).

Chatbots are no longer just a technical novelty for students learning English as a second language. Their use has become a routine part of daily lessons: bots remind students of assignments, suggest new exercises, correct errors, and create a sense of live communication. This creates a learning environment in which language skills develop consistently and naturally. Practical experience shows that chatbots can replace a significant portion of routine language training while maintaining student attention for much longer than traditional textbook assignments.

One of the most in-demand areas is working with written language. Dialogue chatbots offer students a series of exercises, including composing short dialogues, descriptions, mini-texts, and answering questions. The bot not only evaluates the text but also highlights grammatical errors, offers explanations, and provides improved versions. This helps develop a more robust understanding of English sentence structure and develops self-correction skills. Instant feedback is especially valuable: students see errors immediately and can correct them immediately, preventing incorrect constructions from becoming ingrained.

Listening practice is also taking on a new format. Voice bots create short audio messages with accents of varying difficulty, then ask questions to check comprehension. In some cases, they offer to repeat what they heard aloud to improve pronunciation. When the bot detects an awkward pronunciation of a word, it automatically launches a mini-trainer, offering repetitions until the pronunciation is sufficiently clear. As a result, not only listening comprehension but also the skill of correct articulation develops. [5]

One of the most striking examples of practical use is a virtual "conversational partner." This chatbot simulates real-life situations: ordering food, booking accommodations, communicating at the airport, discussing curriculum or hobbies. Each situation unfolds as a full-fledged mini-scene, in which the student must respond to the bot's responses, ask clarifying questions, and complete short tasks. During the dialogue, the bot adapts the difficulty of phrases to the student's level. If the answer is too simple, the bot makes the task more challenging; if difficulties arise, it suggests the appropriate expressions. This form of interaction creates a safe environment where students can practice speaking without fear of judgment or condemnation.

For more structured work, learning scenarios are used—chains of exercises aimed at developing specific skills. For example, when working with vocabulary on the topic "Travel," the bot suggests:

- reviewing flashcards;
- constructing sentences using new expressions;
- choosing the correct option in a test;
- using vocabulary in a mini-dialogue;
- completing a short scenario of a real-life situation.

This sequence ensures consistent and deep learning. If necessary, the bot reminds students to review words after a few days, which helps retain the vocabulary in their long-term memory.

A special focus in the applied part is the creation of written exercises with creative elements. Chatbots prompt students to complete a story, create a dialogue between characters, describe an image, or compose a short letter. After the text is submitted, it is automatically analyzed: strengths are highlighted, inaccuracies are pointed out, and recommendations for improving the structure and vocabulary are given. This approach develops not only linguistic literacy but also creativity.

A real-life example of chatbot use is as follows. The student receives a message: "Imagine this: arriving at a new university. I need to get to know my classmates. How do I start a conversation?" After the student's response, the bot clarifies details ("Where are you from?", "What made you choose this major?") and corrects speech patterns that sound unusual to native speakers. Next, they are given a mini-assignment: formulate five questions that could help them communicate during the first days of school. At the final stage, the bot sends a brief analysis of the dialogue, indicating which phrases sound natural and which could be replaced with more appropriate expressions. This scenario helps students master real-world communication skills.

Analysis of the effectiveness of chatbots shows that regular practice leads to a noticeable increase in language confidence. Students make fewer basic errors, improve their sentence structure, and expand their vocabulary. One of the key advantages is the ability to receive personalized assistance at any time: the bot is always ready to explain a rule, offer a new example, or check a text. This constant availability makes learning flexible and convenient, which is especially valuable for students with busy schedules.

Emotional engagement is an important factor. Chatbots often use gamification elements: levels, points, virtual rewards, timers, and mini-quests. These elements maintain interest and create a sense of progress, which increases motivation. Unlike traditional exercises, interaction with a bot feels more lively, free, and similar to real-world interactions.

The contribution of chatbots to the development of independence is also difficult to overestimate. Students learn to organize their own learning process: choose appropriate tasks, manage their time, analyze their mistakes, and track their progress. Gradually, a habit of regular language practice develops, which is a prerequisite for successfully achieving a high level of English proficiency. Recent research has also explored the integration of chatbots into foreign language education within Kazakhstan. For example, Hamza & Zagidullina investigated the integration of chatbots in foreign language education, highlighting pedagogical implications for student engagement and motivation in language learning contexts. [6]

Experience using chatbots in ESL teaching demonstrates that this tool helps strengthen key language skills and makes the English learning process more flexible, modern, and adaptive. Thanks to the variety of tasks, individual approach and high interactivity, chatbots become a full-fledged assistant that accompanies the student at every stage of language acquisition.[7]

However, the implementation of chatbot technologies in Kazakhstan faces several challenges. These include unequal access to digital resources, insufficient teacher training in AI-based tools, and the lack of localized educational content. Unlike technologically advanced educational systems, Kazakhstani institutions often require methodological adaptation rather than direct adoption of foreign digital solutions. Therefore, the effectiveness of chatbots largely depends on their alignment with national curricula and the pedagogical readiness of teachers.

Results and discussion.

To evaluate the practical effectiveness of AI-based chatbots in ESL teaching, a small-scale pedagogical experiment was conducted. The study was carried out at West Kazakhstan University named after M. Utemisov and involved undergraduate students studying English as a foreign language. The experiment lasted four weeks and aimed to assess the impact of chatbot-assisted learning on the development of students' writing and speaking skills. The participants included 24 students with an intermediate level of English proficiency. The students were divided into two groups: an experimental group (12 students), which used AI-based chatbots for independent practice, and a control group (12 students), which studied using traditional instructional methods. Both groups followed the same curriculum and learning objectives.

The pedagogical experiment consisted of three main stages. During the diagnostic stage, students completed a pre-test designed to assess their initial level of writing and speaking skills. At the formative stage, the experimental group regularly interacted with an AI-based chatbot, completing dialogue-based tasks, short writing assignments, and situational speaking exercises, while the control group practiced the same skills using textbooks and teacher-led activities. At the final stage, a post-test was conducted to measure changes in students' language performance. The assessment of students' progress was based on several criteria, including grammatical accuracy, vocabulary range, coherence of written texts, and fluency of spoken responses. Each criterion was evaluated using a unified scoring scale, allowing for a comparative analysis of the results before and after the experiment.

The results of the experiment demonstrated positive dynamics in the experimental group. Students who used chatbots showed noticeable improvement in writing coherence and confidence in speaking activities. In contrast, the control group demonstrated more moderate progress. These findings suggest that chatbot-assisted learning can enhance the effectiveness of ESL instruction, particularly in supporting independent language practice. A comparative analysis of the pre-test and post-test results revealed measurable improvements in the experimental group. The level of grammatical accuracy increased by approximately 18%, while vocabulary range improved by 21%. Students' written coherence demonstrated a 23% improvement, and speaking fluency increased by 19%. In contrast, the control group showed less significant progress, with average improvements ranging from 7% to 10% across the assessed criteria. These results confirm the positive impact of chatbot-assisted learning on the development of ESL skills.

The future of ai chatbots in language education.

Potential Advances in AI Technology. The future of AI chatbots in language education is poised for revolution thanks to potential advances in AI technology. As machine learning algorithms become increasingly sophisticated and natural language processing capabilities continue to evolve, chatbots are expected to become even more adept at imitating human communication, providing nuanced feedback, and adapting to individual learners' needs in real time. This advancement will likely lead to more personalized and effective language learning, as chatbots will be able to understand and respond to a wider range of linguistic complexities and cultural nuances, thereby enhancing their educational value and becoming indispensable tools in language classrooms.

B. Integrating Chatbots with Other Educational Tools. Integrating chatbots with other educational tools promises to create a more cohesive and dynamic learning ecosystem. By interacting with learning management systems, virtual reality platforms, and interactive language software, chatbots can enhance educational experience by providing seamless communication channels, personalized learning paths, and instant feedback. This synergy enables a more holistic approach to language learning, in which learners can utilize a variety of additional resources and methods, ultimately resulting in a more engaging and effective learning process.

Expanding Access to Language Education with AI-Powered Chatbots
Expanding access to language education with AI-powered chatbots can democratize learning by removing geographic and financial barriers. By offering interactive language practice on a scale, chatbots can reach learners in remote or resource-limited areas, providing them with opportunities to develop language skills that were previously unavailable. This inclusive approach not only expands the audience for language education but also fosters a more diverse and globally connected community of language learners.[8]

Conclusion. This research demonstrated that chatbots are becoming a significant element of modern English as a second language teaching. Their functionality, flexibility, and adaptability to student needs to create a learning environment in which language practice occurs freely, regularly, and without pressure. This article emphasized that chatbots successfully support the development of all core language skills—from writing to speaking—by providing a convenient interaction format and instant feedback.

Of particular value is the ability to simulate real-life communication situations, allowing students to safely practice speaking, expand their vocabulary, and improve grammatical accuracy. It

has been shown that through sequential tasks, creative exercises, and scripted dialogues, chatbots help reinforce learned material and maintain motivation. This leads to greater confidence in English language proficiency, and knowledge acquisition becomes more dynamic and diverse.

The practical application of chatbots demonstrates that digital tools can significantly facilitate learning and complement traditional methods. Students are given the opportunity to work independently, which increases their responsibility for their own progress and fosters a strong habit of regular language practice. The availability of chatbots makes learning more flexible: skills training can be done at any time, which is especially important for those with busy schedules.

This article demonstrates that the potential of chatbots in ESL teaching methods is far from being exhausted. Promising future directions include expanding the emotional support provided by bots, improving speech recognition, integrating bots with virtual or augmented reality, and creating algorithms capable of analyzing individual learning dynamics more deeply and precisely. For the educational system of Kazakhstan, chatbots represent a promising tool for supporting language learning in both secondary and higher education. Their integration can partially compensate for limited classroom interaction and contribute to the development of students' autonomy and digital competence. Such developments will take interaction with chatbots to a new level and ensure even greater effectiveness in English language teaching.

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